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Abstract. Physical activity is a necessary need of a person as well as of any living organism, therefore the development of any sphere of social activity is impossible without the sustainable development of the sphere of physical culture and sports. The need to satisfy a person with physical activity is one of the driving forces for the development of physical culture, in which health is a determining factor. Health with the highest value is the main category that defines the essence of this phenomenon.

Keywords: adaptive physical education, adaptive sports, inclusive education.

Introduction. Human life, like the animal behavior of every living thing and the physiological processes in the body, is guided by physical activity (movement). Restriction of movement, i.e. inactivity, is contrary to the principles of dynamic protection of life, more specifically, to the biological (evolutionary) processes established by nature. The vitality of a person and its quality are completely dependent on the quality of his movement. Therefore, adaptive physical education (kinesiocorrection) plays a very important role in the development of compensatory abilities of people with disabilities, in particular, in the acquisition of certain knowledge, which should contribute to the purposeful production and development of special skills, which will ultimately help people with disabilities learn macroscopic movements and develop In accordance with special types of motor habits and the requirements imposed by public life, because sports and physical education are a necessary condition for the harmonious development of the personality.

Tasks. The task of the research was to find out the social importance and condition of adaptive physical education and adaptive sports for people with disabilities in the reality of Georgia.

Methods. The methods of information search, theoretical analysis and generalization were used.

Review. Today, the greatest attention is paid to the development of adaptive physical education and adaptive sports, in this regard, Georgia is not a representative of disabled people, physical activity, in the form of adaptive physical education and sports, is of vital importance. Adaptive physical education is an integral part of complex rehabilitation for persons with retardation in physical development. It is especially important for those with musculoskeletal and neuromuscular impairments, paresis and paralysis. Adaptive physical culture is intended for people with deviations in physical development, including people with disabilities, and includes a whole complex of sports-rehabilitation activities aimed at the rehabilitation and social integration of this category of people, overcoming psychological barriers that oppose the perception of a full-fledged life. One of the most successful directions of adaptive physical culture is adaptive physical education and adaptive sports, the main goal of which is the formation of movement activity as biological, psychological and social factors on the human body and its personal qualities. When familiarizing with scientific research, it is clear that, in addition to

physical culture and sports researchers, in such fields of science as rehabilitation, valiology, psychology, defectology, biomechanics, medicine, etc. show a great interest in adaptive physical education and adaptive sports.

Adaptive sport is one of the types of adaptive physical culture, which helps to satisfy the need for self-actualization of a person and to combine one's abilities with the abilities of other people. The main task of adaptive sports is the formation of people's sports culture, getting used to the social-historical experience in the given field, studying the technological, intellectual and other values of physical culture as well as strengthening health and rehabilitation-corrective means for people with similar problems. The essence of adaptive sports is in the development, correction and rehabilitation of impaired functional systems and organs of people with disabilities, and then in achieving the highest sports results in competing with people with similar problems.

Fig. 1. Physical education should be more than just 'gym class'

Adaptive sports have two directions: rehabilitation-recreational sports and sports of the highest achievements. The first one is developed at school, and sports of the highest achievements are developed in relevant sports and health organizations. Practice teaches us that if movement activity is a normal, daily need for healthy people, physical exercises are a vital necessity for people with disabilities to the extent that movement activity and mostly physical exercises are a very effective means and method of social rehabilitation for physical development and social adaptation at the same time.

Physical exercise is a powerful means of beneficial effects on the human body and expands the range of possibilities over time. First of all, it expands the possibilities of sustainable defects and development of the range of motion. We can cite many examples from practice, when under the influence of physical exercises and special training, children with intellectual disabilities correct their impaired speech, master complex gymnastic movements, and blind people move boldly and confidently in space. Children with severe cerebral palsy begin to walk and talk after gymnastics and swimming lessons. People using wheelchairs achieve the greatest sports results

on the international stage, and all this comes as a result of tireless and professionally calculated program adaptive physical education and sports training.

Adaptive sports have a deep and multifaceted influence on the essential aspects of a person, developing him both physically and spiritually. This is a long process of personal formation of a person, which inculcates and accumulates moral values, norms, traditions, ideals, sports behavior norms and laws in a person. All these are individual experiences accumulated from social life in sports. The very essence of the term "involvement" in sports is closely related to socialization, to the extent that in the process of interaction, the values and experiences given by the society are assimilated and realized in their lives, with which society they had to connect their sports life. Socialization is particularly clearly revealed in the process of sports athletes, which can be considered as a form of their social activity, in the process of which such social values as victory, prestige, sympathy, dedication to a common cause, respect and support of teammates and opponents (i.e., people in general) are created, the joy of a common victory. and also the sharing of regrets caused by common defeat, etc.

Sport is a special world of communication and acquaintance for people with disabilities, which captures their consciousness and focuses attention on new objects, weaves their psyche in brighter colors, relieves their mood and creates a special atmosphere of emotions. It is an active creative process where people with disabilities have the opportunity to develop their own physical development and perfect their aesthetic views. They try to create their own unique face, where they put the harmony of courage and strength of spirit. This gives their lifestyle a new color, new colors and forces them to evaluate their own personality, their own "I". It allows him to feel like a full-fledged person and a useful member of his society.

Social progress always requires revision, adjustment or change of the existing. But any changes should be based on a deep analysis, proper foresight of expected risks and drawing of appropriate conclusions. Social formative changes have a great impact on all aspects of social life, but any changes should be aimed at changing the situation for the better. This also applies to school physical education, the importance of which in the all-round, harmonious development and upbringing of children and adolescents is undefined, especially for children with disabilities, since the issue of physical activity and adaptive physical education is an event of vital importance. But we must not forget that any action has a backlash, which Afgil had at the initial stage of the reform started in the education system of Georgia in 2004, which provided for the integration of disabled students with healthy children within the framework of inclusive education. In this regard, the mentioned reform has undoubtedly brought many positive changes for students with disabilities in terms of breaking through "alienation" and "locked-in" and uncomplicated relationship with their peers, the neglect of which prevents the development of civil coexistence of two societies, which is the main driving force for the development of society in general. However, the implementation of such tender and important programs requires a very serious, large-scale and well-thought-out description in time. In fact, all these preparatory tasks were forced at the time, as a result of which the above-mentioned integration process was met by unprepared students, parents and teachers, school infrastructure and program part. Over time, many things in this regard have been sorted out and changed for the better (including the retraining of teachers), although certain problems still remain, as the said contingent requires special attention and an individual approach, due to the peculiarities of diseases or physical defects. This means that for every nysology, a specific, individual, adaptive physical education

method is needed, which should take into account the peculiarities of kinesio correction and kinesotherapy.

Conclusion. Physical activity is the driving force of human life as well as any living thing. Movement inactivity contradicts the biological processes established by nature, since the quality of human vitality is completely dependent on the quality of its movement. Therefore, adaptive physical education and adaptive sports play an extremely important role in the development of compensatory abilities of people with disabilities, in particular. In the acquisition of certain knowledge, which should contribute to the purposeful generation and development of special skills, which will ultimately teach people with disabilities corrective movements and develop specific types of motor habits in accordance with the needs imposed by private and public life, sports and physical education are essential conditions for the harmonious development of personality.

Literature

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